

Comprehensive evaluation of *Lagerstroemia indica* L. in terms of scenic characteristics in Tashkent conditions

Amanbaeva Shakhlo (doctoral student)

Tolayev Doniyor (Phd)

ANNOTATION

Lagerstroemia indica L. grows late in Tashkent compared to other plants and begins to bud in the second half of April. It was observed that the seasonal changes in *Lagerstroemia indica* L. depend on the growth and development of the plant. *Lagerstroemia indica* L. is the most beautiful and long-flowering plant of the garden collection. 2-3-year-old young branches are planted in an open place, and if the top branches are cut, the side branches grow well and take on a unique shape.

Key words: *Lagerstroemia indica* L., phenological observation, methodology, vegetative, pollination, fertilization, geographic, spectrum, meteorological, criterion, complex, morphological, vegetation.

Research methods. Phenological observations I.N. Beideman "Методика изучения фенологии растений", "Vegetative reproduction of plants" developed by M. Browse for the purpose of vegetative reproduction of trees and shrubs, assessment of the scenic quality It was made based on the N.I.Shtonda style. Generally accepted criteria for statistical processing of received data and B.A. Dospikhov is performed according to the "Методика полевого опыта" method.

As a result of the research, it was observed that the seasonal changes in *Lagerstroemia indica* L. depend on the growth and development of the plant. Its shape depends on the way it is cut. Generally quite resistant to shaping and cutting. After the pruning is completed, the vigorous branches will form annuals and then

produce numerous purple-pink curly flowers. During this period, the leaves grow and develop more. In this case, the formation of new leaves and branches coincided with the month of March and April. The period of budding is May-June, flowering of cypress is July-October, fruit formation is September-October, fruit shedding is October-November, and old leaves are shedding November-December are listed in table 1.

Table 1

**Seasonal changes in Lagerstroemia indica L
(Observations were carried out in 2023)**

The name of a scenic bush.	Swelling of growing buds			Leaf development				Flowering			fruit (seed) ripening and shedding				Stem growth.					
	The beginning of aphid movement	Bulging.	Opening.	Formation of new shoots.	The emergence of leaves.	The leaves should be	The beginning of jaundice.	Total jaundice.	The beginning of the spill.	The end of the spill.	The beginning of flowering.	The end of flowering.	Flowering rate.	Fruit ripening.	Completion of ripening.	The beginning of the spill.	The end of the spill.	Productivity level.	Beginning	Ending
Lagerstroemia	25.III	5.IV	12.IV	20.V	12.IV	24.IV	25.VIII	15.XI	5.XI	10.XII	15.VI	25.X	5a'1o	25.VIII	30.IX	10.IX	24.X	3o'rtu	10.IV	20IX

In order to study the life of trees and shrubs and seasonal events in them, the following observations are made:

- the beginning of sap movement in the body of plants;
- swelling of leaf buds and flower buds;
- writing buds;
- emergence of new buds;
- the appearance of the primary-first leaf;

- full opening of leaves;
- development of flower buds, beginning to open, full opening and opening
- pollination and fertilization
- ripening of fruits and seeds;
- shedding and spreading of fruits and seeds;
- growth and cessation of growth of branches.
- emergence of new buds
- development of flower buds
- the beginning and complete yellowing of leaves in autumn;
- the leaves begin to fall;
- complete shedding of leaves;
- the period of winter break is studied

Aphid activity on monitored trees is determined by cutting deeply into the tree trunk. The appearance of drops at the cut site is recorded in the observation log as the day of sap movement. Pheno-observations can be conducted on one or a group of trees. In order to clearly see the phenological phases of a tree species in a certain geographical area, it is appropriate to describe them in the form of a phenological spectrum. Phenological observations are of great scientific and practical value for forestry and greening. Phenological observations are complemented by meteorological data, which allows for accurate interpretation of annual changes.

In the assessment of the scenic characteristics of the *Lagerstroemia indica* L. bush, the assessment of the forms growing in the field was carried out based on the process of phenological observation according to the method of N.I. Shtonda. In this case, the bushes were evaluated according to the point system according to the criterion.

2 - table

Results of a comprehensive assessment of *Lagerstroemia indica* L. for its decorativeness

The name of the bush	Indicators are serial numbers and points assigned to them											Total points	Landscape level	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11			

<i>Lagerstroemia indica</i> L.	6	2	6	2	6	14	16	8	6	8	8	82	1
-----------------------------------	---	---	---	---	---	----	----	---	---	---	---	----	---

The main decorative features of the *Lagerstroemia indica* L. bush were indicators such as the appearance of flowering, the duration of flowering, the color of the fruit and its long storage in the bush. According to the duration of the preservation period, the scenic feature of the bush during the vegetation period was evaluated at 8 points.

Lagerstroemia indica L. bush was evaluated as a high ornamental bush (YuM) with 82 points according to the comprehensive evaluation of its scenic characteristics.

From the studied research, it became known that we got information about the flowers, leaves, fruits and seeds of *Lagerstroemia indica* L., morphological structure, relationship with the environment and vegetation period. *Lagerstroemia indica* L. is a beautiful flowering shrub, resistant to heat, cold, and drought, and is not picky about soil. Flowers bloom from June to October-November.

At present, a lot of attention is being paid to landscaping and beautification, as well as forestry. Greening of the streets and avenues of our city, implementation of these activities in remote areas, selection of plant species suitable for the soil of the areas is considered one of the important issues. We recommend that the Indian nastrini bush can grow in almost all regions of our country under the climatic conditions. From the above data, we can see that the species meets these requirements.

USED LITERATURE

1. Вилданова К.Д., Штонда Н.И., Каримов А.Р. Декоративные кустарники. – Ташкент. 2006. – С 72.
2. Галактионов И.И., Ву А.В., Осин В.А. Декоративная дендрология. – Москва. 1967. - С – 253 - 254.
3. Ёзиев Л.Х. Особенности формирования и качество семян интродуцированных древесных растений Южного Узбекистана // Бюл. Глав. Ботан. Сада. 1996. - №124 – С 54-58.

4. Зокиров Қ.З., Жамолхонов Х.А. Ботаникадан русча-ўзбекча энциклопедик ЛУҒАТ.
5. Качалов А.А. Деревя и кустарники. – Москва. 1970. – 161.
6. Колесников А.И. Декоративная дендрология. – Москва. 1974. - С – 391 - 392.
7. Корчагина А.М., Кузимурадов Қ.Қ. Поведения некоторых восточноазиатский древесно кустарников растений в условиях Узбекистана. № Вып 22. – Ташкент. 1988. –С 24-30.